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**ON THE STATE OF LEGALITY AND PRACTICE OF PROSECUTOR'S
SUPERVISION OVER THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MIGRATION LEGISLATION
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF BASHKORTOSTAN)**

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The paper analyzes the state of legality in the implementation of migration legislation in Russia. The authors noted that migration processes on the territory of modern Russia play an important role in its economic development. Due to the huge migration flows, the state of law in this area is poor. All this leads to the fact that state bodies pay special attention to monitoring the implementation of legislation in this area. The Prosecutor's Office of the Russian Federation is called upon to play an important role in countering illegal migration.

Keywords: migration, legislation, foreign citizens, prosecutor's supervision, violation of rights.

**О СОСТОЯНИИ ЗАКОННОСТИ И ПРАКТИКЕ ПРОКУРОРСКОГО НАДЗОРА
ЗА ИСПОЛНЕНИЕМ МИГРАЦИОННОГО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВА
(НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БАШКОРТОСТАН)**

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В работе анализируется состояние законности в сфере исполнением миграционного законодательства в России. Авторами отмечено, что миграционные процессы на территории современной России играют важную роль в ее экономическом развитии. Из-за огромных миграционных потоков состояние законности в этой области оставляет желать лучшего. Все это приводит к тому, что государственные органы уделяют особое внимание контролю за исполнением законодательства в этой сфере. Важную роль в противодействии незаконной миграции призвана играть прокуратура РФ.

Ключевые слова: миграция, законодательство, иностранные граждане, прокурорский надзор, нарушение прав.

Migration processes in modern realities have a large-scale and international level. The flow of migrants from the Middle East and Africa to the EU countries has intensified and become uncontrollable. The Russian Federation, despite the not entirely favorable financial and economic situation, the tightening of legislation in the field of labor activity, nevertheless, continues to remain attractive to migrants, especially from neighboring countries.

Now in Russia seven million foreign citizens live, more than 700 thousand citizens from the CIS

countries are illegally [1]. Illegal migration poses a serious threat to security, public law and order, since illegal migrants do not lend themselves to state registration, are excluded from the system of official employment, the system of taxation, social protection of a person, which in turn involves their introduction into the shadow sector of the economy.

The prosecutor's office is called upon to play an important role in countering illegal migration, since the norms of migration legislation are violated by both migrants and government officials.

Supervisory measures taken by the prosecutor's office in the framework of monitoring the implementation of legislation in the field of migration, as well as measures to respond to violations, are the main guarantee of achieving a balance between all areas of public relations related to migration.

As examples of the most typical violations in the activities of the internal affairs bodies, the following can be noted:

- foreign citizens and stateless persons are not timely put or removed from the migration registration at the place of stay, and this information is not entered into the state information system of migration registration and is not sent to the tax authorities;

- no checks are made on the addresses of registration of foreign citizens and stateless persons on migration registration;

- no administrative proceedings are initiated against employers when it is revealed that migrants carry out labor activities without a work permit;

- the passports of foreign citizens are illegally confiscated.

Numerous violations are revealed in the Department for Migration Issues of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Russian Federation. Thus, according to the results of the prosecutor's inspection, the employees of the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Bashkortostan revealed violations when granting permits to attract and use the labor of foreign workers; in 2020, more than 400 violations of migration legislation by employers were detected by employers. The deadlines for preparing and sending to the Ministry of Family, Labor and Social Protection of the Republic of Bashkortostan requests for providing opinions on the involvement and use of foreign workers were not met [1].

There are cases of abuse by the employees of the Migration Department of the powers granted to them: in the overwhelming majority of cases, when obtaining passports, it was required to provide documents that were not provided for by the current rules of law. Thus, the prosecutor's office of the Iglinsky district of the Republic of Bashkortostan revealed that 20 foreign citizens sent applications to the regional department for migration

issues in Bashkortostan for the provision of documents for temporary residence and adoption into the citizenship of the Russian Federation. In the list of necessary documents, these persons provided the decisions of the Iglinsky District Court, which established the fact of permanent residence in the territory of the country of these persons from the near abroad. As it turned out, civil cases based on the applications of foreign citizens were not submitted to the court and the corresponding decisions were not made. On the basis of these forged documents, 10 of these persons received a residence permit, another 8 - citizenship of the Russian Federation. In order to exclude the established violations of the law, the district prosecutor's office filed a statement of claim with the court on the recognition of the decisions of the migration service as illegal. The court satisfied the arguments of the prosecutor's office and made appropriate decisions on the statements of claim [2].

Foreign citizens violate the deadlines for registration with migration registration, they indicate false information in their applications. Thus, the Krasnokamsky District Prosecutor's Office monitored the implementation of migration legislation in the indicated territory. It was revealed that in the period from May to September of this year, a 45-year-old citizen presented to the migration service fake notifications of temporary residence and a fictitious certificate of registration of property rights. In reality, the said citizen did not own the said dwelling, because he sold it in April of this year. On the basis of the submitted documents, 9 citizens of the near abroad were registered in a residential building with an area of about 40 square meters, the above-named persons never lived at the indicated address. On the basis of this, the district prosecutor's office conducted an inspection necessary to clarify the issue of initiating a criminal case under Art. 322.1 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation (organization of illegal migration). Cases of permissive control over foreign citizens in respect of whom the time of stay on the territory of the Russian Federation expires are established [3].

Prosecutors also regularly reveal the facts of workers' residence at construction sites, in auxiliary and other non-residential premises at the place

of work that do not comply with sanitary and epidemiological rules and fire safety requirements.

Thus, the Belebeevskaya interdistrict prosecutor's office carried out an audit of the implementation of migration legislation in the work of the company Garant LLC. Based on the requirements of the law, foreign citizens permanently or temporarily residing in Russia must be registered at the address of residence and taken into account at the address of stay. However, the director of a commercial company used 10 citizens of Uzbekistan in the construction of a residential building in the city of Belebey, without fulfilling the specified requirements of the legislation.

Of particular relevance, in the light of the constant informatization of modern society, is the work to suppress activities aimed at legalizing illegal migration in the information and telecommunications network "Internet".

At present, with the active development and use of the Internet by an unlimited number of persons, the issues of illegal migration, registration of permits by illegal means require proper resolution. There are acute issues of timely and effective supervision by the prosecutor's office over information posted on Internet sites, which outlines the possibilities and methods of violating the procedure established by the legislator for legal stay on the territory of the Russian Federation, employment of foreign persons, obtaining a certain list of documents required for submission to relevant supervisory bodies. There are facts of proposals to conclude fictitious marriages by foreign citizens and stateless persons with citizens of the Russian Federation in order to obtain a temporary residence permit without taking into account the quota.

So, the prosecutor of the Ermekeyevsky district of the Republic of Bashkortostan carried out an inspection of the implementation of migration legislation, during which the website «https://vk.com/brak_ua» was revealed, information on the provision of services for concluding fake marriages with foreign citizens or persons was revealed at the indicated e-mail address with the absence of citizenship of any state, these marriages were concluded for registration in the territory of the Russian Federation and (or) citizenship of Russia in

a more accessible and faster manner, which helps to legalize registration in the territory of the Russian Federation and (or) citizenship of Russia in a simplified manner.

Thus, at present, the law provides for the need to restrict access to data that contains contacts of persons and information on the provision of assistance in registration of invalid marriages with foreign citizens or stateless persons in an attempt to register registration on the territory of the Russian Federation and (or) Russian citizenship for more quick and easy way. At the same time, prosecutorial supervision has a preventive focus, which contributes to ensuring security and law and order, preventing socio-economic tension and interethnic conflicts.

Among the most important problems of prosecutorial supervision in the field of implementation of migration legislation, it is necessary to highlight the problems of low efficiency of prosecutor's supervision in this area in relation to individual entrepreneurs and legal entities that use migrant labor. In particular, the prosecutor's office should carry out checks on commercial and non-commercial enterprises that use illegal labor of migrants. However, as a rule, the prosecution authorities pay more attention to the implementation of migration legislation by private (natural) persons, while the guilty employers evade responsibility.

In the conditions of modern Russia, the methods and means of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of migration legislation should be constantly improved. One of the directions is to increase the level of interdepartmental cooperation, which makes it possible to respond in a timely manner to violations of migration legislation, both by state bodies and individuals. Of no small importance in this process is the improvement of the regulatory and legal framework, including on the main definition of the main directions of supervision in the field of migration. In general, taking into account the current migration situation, the prosecutor's office at a high level cope with the tasks of supervision in this area.

The preventive component of prosecutorial supervision plays an important role in the normal functioning of Russian society, since migrants are an integral part of it. Prosecutor's response mea-

sures prevent the growth of tension in those constituent entities of the Russian Federation where the number of migrants is significant. This method of supervision plays a significant role in maintaining law and order and ensuring security, preventing socio-economic tension and ethnic conflicts.

The problem of the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision of compliance with legislation in the field of migration by individual entrepreneurs and participants in medium-sized businesses is due to the large volume of labor of migrants by these participants in economic relations, the lack of control or connivance in relation to individual

entrepreneurs by state bodies and the public.

Thus, today the situation in the migration sphere as a whole remains rather complicated. There are numerous violations of the law committed by officials of the territorial bodies of the Migration Directorate of the Russian MIA Administration in the exercise of their powers, as well as by commercial and non-commercial organizations. Particular attention should be paid to verifying the completeness, timeliness and legality of decisions made by authorized government bodies on applications from citizens of the Russian Federation and foreign citizens.

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